

Perception of Female Social Studies Students on Implications of Substance Abuse on Socio-Emotional Adjustments of Victims in Colleges of Education, North-West, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study assessed perception of female Social Studies students on implications of substance abuse on socio-emotional aspects with specific regards to Social and emotional adjustments of victims in Colleges of Education in North-West, Nigeria. The research design employed for this study was descriptive survey design and the study used a structured questionnaire for data collection from female social studies students. The instrument utilized in this research underwent a rigorous validation process to ensure its content, structure, and face validity from supervisors and experts in English and statistics for their evaluation. A pilot study was conducted with 30 undergraduate Social Studies students. These students, who served as pilot respondents, were not part of the study sample. The reliability coefficient was determined using Cronbach's alpha method and the analysis revealed a reliability coefficient of 0.795 for the instrument. The population of the study was 2798 NCE Social Studies female students and sample size of the study was 333 based on Improved Research Advisor (2010). The researcher employed proportionate sampling techniques in which six (6) colleges were proportionately chosen, and the required sample size was then selected from these Colleges of Education. A total of 333 respondents were issued with the questionnaire but 304 successfully completed their copies making 91.3% response rate used for the study. Data collected were analyzed with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) IBM version 26. Statistical procedures used included frequencies and percentages, means and standard deviation. Findings revealed substance abuse has significant and negative influence on social and emotional adjustment of female Social Studies students involved in the act within the selected Colleges of Education. Among others it was found that substance abuse negatively influences socio-emotional aspects of female Social Studies students involved. The study concluded that substance abuse has major negative influences on social adjustment and emotional adjustment of the female students involved in the act within the selected Colleges of Education. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that management of the Colleges should institute periodic orientation on drug abuse for students along guidance and counseling for students in Colleges of Education within the North West zone in Nigeria.

Keywords: Perception, Social Studies, Substance Abuse, Socio-emotional Adjustment, and Victims.

Introduction

The social, economic, and health fabric of families, society, and the nation as a whole are all seriously threatened by drug abuse. The usage of drugs by its population affects almost every nation in the world. The rise in drug addiction on a global scale has created issues such as an increase in crime and violence, and an increase in viruses like the Hepatitis B and C virus and HIV/AIDS, and it has also contributed to the disintegration of our communities' social structures. Drug misuse is a serious issue that worries parents, sociologists, religious leaders, counselors, and others involved in education. Due to the growing rise of juvenile involvement and, as of today, female involvement, it is a sensitive national and worldwide concern that requires urgent attention.

Chronic drug use can result in substantial, often irreparable, physical and societal harm (either temporarily or for a long period). Additionally, there could be inside harm. As a result, some of the undergraduates in colleges of education and other tertiary institutions who are still in their formative years, spiral into madness, become social outcasts at school, and ultimately quit. Drug abuse refers to prescription abuse, self-medication, and the use of illicit substances. Some of these compounds, in the form of medications, provide users with pleasure, and some end users are brain nerves (known as pleasurable pathways). Any chemical that, when taken by a living organism, has the potential to alter one or more of the socio-emotional, psychological, or physiological processes of that organism is considered a drug.

Nearly 15% of Nigeria's adult population (around 14.3 million individuals) reported using psychoactive drugs "considerably" in the past year, which is significantly more than the 2016 global average of 5.6 percent for adults. The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) provided technical assistance for the survey, which was coordinated by Nigeria's National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and the Center for Research and Information on Substance Abuse with financing from the European Union. Cannabis was the most often used drug, and it was found that drug use was highest among those between the ages of 25 and 39. Additionally mentioned were sedatives, heroin, cocaine, and the non-medical use of prescription opioids (Kazeem & Basse, 2019).

Social adjustment is an individual's attempt to adjust to the demands, norms, and values of society to be accepted. In a technical sense, adjustment or social adjustment refers to interacting as amicably as possible with others. Emotional adjustment is basically the response to a person, object, or event and are expressed in a variety of ways such as anger, fear, joy, love, happiness, and sadness among others. Emotional adjustment is also called personal adjustment.

Statement of the problem

Drug and substance misuse is a recognized threat having major consequences for people's health, security, social-economic well-being, and cultural well-being on a global and even regional scale. Students have repeatedly demonstrated that drug and substance misuse are quite prevalent in Nigeria, with different degrees of preference for both general and particular drug usage. Some of these commonly abused substances include cigarettes, alcohol, cocaine, mandrax, and heroin.

As drug usage among young people increases in Nigeria, they are more frequently turning to strong combinations of numerous narcotics, which carry a significant risk of deadly overdose. As an illustration, "gutter water" is a commonly used concoction of medications that combines codeine, tramadol, Rohypnol, cannabis, and either water or juice. In addition, some young adults are turning to unsanitary alternatives including smoking lizard parts and excrement and inhaling glue, gasoline, sewage, and urine. Numerous reports indicate that the rate of substance abuse among Nigerian youth is rising, with a large proportion of women involved. Women are expected to serve as role models who

pass on societal norms and values to the next generation, as well as tools for modifying an individual's socio-emotional and psychological makeup, but the rise in substance abuse among women may have negative effects on development.

Therefore, this study hinges on the perceptions of social studies female students regarding the implications of substance abuse on socio-emotional aspects of students using a survey method.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to:

- i. Find out the views of female Social Studies students on the influence of substance abuse on social adjustment among female students in colleges of education in North-West, Nigeria.
- ii. Find out the views of female Social Studies students on the influence of substance abuse on emotional adjustment among female students in colleges of education in North-West Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered for the study:

- i. What are the views of female Social Studies students on the influence of substance abuse on social adjustment among female Social Studies students in colleges of education in North-West, Nigeria?
- ii. What are the views of female Social Studies Students on the influence of substance abuse on emotional adjustment among female Social Studies students in colleges of education in North-West Nigeria?

Scope of the study

The scope of this study is limited to the perception of female Social Studies students on implications of substance abuse on socio-emotional aspects in colleges of education in North-West, Nigeria. There are many variables relating to socio-emotional aspects but this research is limited to social adjustment and emotional adjustment among social studies female students in colleges of education in North-West Nigeria. The study covered the Nigerian Certificate of Education female Social Studies students level three (NCE III) in the North-West Geo-political Zone of Nigeria.

Introduction

Here, this study reviewed relevant literatures related to this study and amongst them includes an ego/self-theory, concept of social studies, concept of social adjustment and emotional adjustment, concept of substance abuse, substance abuse in Nigeria, implications of substance abuse on students in colleges of education and lastly socio-emotional implications of substance abuse.

An Ego/Self Theory of Substance Dependence

According to Khantzian's (1974) thesis, drug abuse is closely related to a person's attempts to deal with both their internal emotional and outward social and physical environments. According to a modern psychoanalytic perspective, the best way to comprehend drug dependency is to look at how a person's ego structure and sense of self-serve, undermine their attempts to cope, as well as how the distinct effects of various drugs help or hinder these efforts. The majority of the early psychoanalytic formulations of substance dependence focused on the instinctive, pleasurable aspects of drug use to explain the compelling nature of addiction, even though early psychoanalytic investigators recognized the presence of underlying depression, tension, and distress in addicts.

Concept of Social Studies Education

Social Studies as a social science discipline has no universally accepted definition, but different authorities in the field have given their definitions which Ogundare (2014) said are classified into three groups. He said Social Studies definitions can be according to the contents of Social Studies, definitions according to the purpose of Social Studies, and definitions according to the methods of Social Studies. To him, some other definitions try to combine any two of the above or all three categories. For any Social Studies definition to be accepted and used, it must talk about man and his relation to the environment, both physical and social.

Concept of Social Adjustment

Individuals must adapt to the social norms of the demanding society of today. Mature social relationships, successful academic endeavors, and healthy psychological development are all influenced by having good social ties and social skills. A peaceful relationship with others and adherence to the social norms of the home, peer groups, culture, and community are examples of social adjustment. According to Mazahevi, Baghiyan, and Fatehizadeh (2006), social adjustment is the most beneficial component of adjustment, even though it includes many other elements such as social, emotional, physical, and educational dimensions.

Concept of Emotional Adjustment

The act of accepting and adjusting to one's circumstances, which may call for a change in perspective and the proper expression of emotions in a particular situation, is known as emotional adjustment. Emotional adjustment is the maintenance of emotional balance in the face of internal and external pressures. This is facilitated by cognitive mechanisms of adaptation and acceptance. An illustration would be maintaining emotional control and coping mechanisms while experiencing an identity crisis. This ability is crucial to mental health and can result in psychopathology and mental illness if it is damaged or underdeveloped.

Concept of Drug/Substance Abuse

Ajayi and Ayodele (2003) define drug misuse as the improper or improper use of chemicals that have the ability to alter how cells in the body function. According to Bayer (quoted in Egbochuku and Akerele 2007), stimulants are chemicals that excite specific central nervous system functions. Stimulants are compounds that raise the activity of an organ in the body. According to Ajayi and Ekundayo (2010), substance addiction is also defined as excessive reliance on and misuse of a single drug, whether or not a competent health professional has previously diagnosed the condition. Additionally, they noted that among the drugs frequently taken by young people are harmful substances like cocaine, Indian hemp (marijuana), morphine, heroin, tobacco, ephedrine, valium five, and Chinese pills.

Substance Abuse in Nigeria

Substance abuse among youths in Nigeria is a growing concern with various factors contributing to its prevalence. Motives for drug abuse are categorized as sociological, psychological, curiosity, boredom, fear alleviation, pursuit of pleasure, and family background. Despite the acknowledged adverse effects on youth, the number of undergraduates using stimulants has risen. Reasons for stimulant usage include the need to belong, expectancy, mental set, sex, drives, integrative use, ceremonial use, hedonistic use, utilitarian use, and disintegrative use. Some students use drugs for stress relief and self-medication for nighttime studying.

Regarding drug use in Nigeria an estimated 14.4 percent (range 14 percent - 14.8 percent) of the population in Nigeria, or 14.3 million people between 15 and 64 years of age had used drugs, excluding alcohol and tobacco, in 2017. This estimate includes people who had used a drug at least once in the

past 12 months as well as high-risk drug users.¹¹ The estimates have been adjusted to account for individuals who had used more than one drug, in other words, "any drug use" counts individuals only once even if they had used multiple substances in the past year. As a result, the sum of individual drug estimates will add to a number greater than the estimated total (Oshodi, Aina, and Onajole (2020).

Implications of Substance Abuse on Students in Colleges of Education

Drugs are utilized for various reasons, and numerous studies have established a range of effects associated with substance abuse. Physical consequences of drug misuse include liver cirrhosis, pancreatic and peptic ulcers, hypertension, neurological disorders, and tuberculosis. Additionally, mental effects encompass retardation, growth deformities, nervous system deficiencies, delayed motor development, amnesia, and dementia, among others (Mba, 2018). The devastating consequences of drug addiction or abuse are of great concern to both national and international organizations worldwide, particularly concerning the alarming spread of this issue among young people.

These consequences include mental disorders, social violence, gang formation, cultism, armed robbery, 419 syndrome, internet fraud, social miscreants (area boys and girls), youth lawlessness, lack of respect for elders, rape, loss of senses, instant death, and the tragic waste of precious and innocent lives, among many others (Dankani, 2022). The effects of smoking tobacco are dependent on the absorption of nicotine from the smoke. Many students progress from tobacco smoking to marijuana use, believing it to be more potent and capable of inducing hyperactivity. Marijuana is easily obtainable from drug peddlers who increasingly target the youth, often using it as a symbol of rebellion. Drug addicts can become a nuisance to society and a burden to themselves and their families. There are noticeable changes in the physical appearance, behavior, and overall health of an addict, including signs of emaciation, malnourishment, neglect of personal hygiene, and an unkempt appearance. Drug-addicted adolescents tend to associate with fellow addicts, and drug addiction is not only expensive but also difficult to sustain. The social problem of substance abuse among young males and females often leads to varying degrees of physical and psychological dependence, resulting in complete withdrawal from schools and the emergence of future criminals and illiterates in society (Schmallegger, 2016; Fareo, 2022).

Socio-emotional Implications of Substance Abuse

Socio-emotional aspects involve an individual's ability to initiate, maintain, and respond to social interactions, building relationships with people in their lives, including parents, relatives, and friends. These interactions can be temporary or long-term, occurring with both familiar and unfamiliar individuals. They encompass a range of abilities—from managing communication and handling stress or adversity to fostering positive relationships and connecting with peers, often through verbal and non-verbal communication.

Substance abuse carries wide-ranging consequences—social, economic, psychological, cultural, physical, moral, and health-related—which can ultimately result in poverty, disability, social maladjustment, or even death. Chinkere and Mayowa (2011) highlighted that, aside from chronic illnesses that may emerge after years of excessive drinking, alcohol is also linked to traumatic incidents that can cause disability or death at a relatively young age.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2019), substance abuse is a key factor contributing to the global burden of disease. They observed that nearly one-third of the adult disease burden can be traced to behaviors formed during adolescence. WHO (2019) further noted that alcohol may have particularly severe and immediate effects on young people, partly because their muscle mass is generally smaller than that of adults. In addition, Oshodi, Aina, and Onajole (2020) reported that excessive caffeine consumption has been linked to "brain fatigue syndrome," a culture-specific

condition observed among West African students. This syndrome is characterized by poor learning retention, physical complaints involving the head and neck, and visual disturbances.

Methodology

This study employed descriptive survey research design and the population of the study consists of 2798 female social studies students in ten (10) colleges of education, North-West Nigeria. Proportionate sampling technique was used to draw the sample size of 333 as recommended by Improved Research Advisors (2010) table for determining sample size. A structured questionnaire was used as the instrument for the study and 333 questionnaire was issued but 304 was successfully completed and returned and thus comprise of 91.3% response rate used for the study. The data collected for this study was analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 23. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions.

Data Analysis and presentation

Research Question One: Perception of female students' views on the influence of substance abuse on social adjustment among Social Studies students in the selected Colleges of Education.

To find the influence of substance abuse on social adjustment among the female Social Studies students in the selected Colleges of Education, the expressed rated opinions of the respondents were classified in frequencies and percentages, mean and standard deviation were then computed as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Perceived substance abuse influence on social adjustment among Social Studies female students in the selected Colleges of Education by respondents (n=304)

S/N	Influence of substance abuse on social adjustment	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev.
1	Substance abuse enhances the willingness of female students to address social problems.	90(29.6)	103(33.9)	62(20.4)	49(16.1)	2.77	1.047
2	With the aid of substance abuse, good friendships are promoted among female students.	53(17.4)	106(34.9)	72(23.7)	73(24.0)	2.46	1.040
3	Substance abuse hinders capacity to participate in social activities and events among female students.	7		77(25.3)	28(9.2)	2.82	0.919
4	Most females engaged in substance abuse display antisocial behaviours.	87(28.6)	162(53.3)	41(13.5)	14(4.6)	3.06	0.777
5	Substance abuse increases the likelihood of forming friendships among female students.	55(18.1)	117(38.5)	87(28.6)	45(14.8)	2.60	0.949
6	Females engaged in substance abuse often encounter conflicts and disagreements in their interpersonal relationships.	118(38.8)	132(43.4)	44(14.5)	10(3.3)	3.18	0.797
7	Substance abuse contributes to the neglect of cultural values within our society.	147(48.4)	98(32.2)	46(15.1)	13(4.3)	3.25	0.865
8	Females engaged in substance abuse are often excluded from certain social groups	122(40.1)	129(42.4)	41(13.5)	12(3.9)	3.19	0.813
9	Most female engaged in substance abuse do not exhibit antisocial behaviours.	62(20.4)	109(35.9)	105(34.5)	28(9.2)	2.67	0.902
10	I think that reducing or avoiding substance abuse would positively impact females' social interactions and adjustment.	154(50.7)	96(31.6)	36(11.8)	18(5.9)	3.27	0.890
Aggregate mean						2.93	0.420

(Benchmark = 2.50)

The above table presents findings on the impact of substance abuse on social adjustment among Social Studies female students in selected Colleges of Education. Respondents generally agree that substance abuse has multi-dimensional influences on social adjustment. Some positive aspects include an enhanced willingness to address social problems, but the consensus is not in favor of promoting good friendships. Substance abuse is seen as hindering participation in social activities and events, leading to antisocial behaviors. However, there is acknowledgment that substance abuse may increase the likelihood of forming friendships. Conflicts and disagreements in interpersonal relationships, as well as neglect of cultural values, are associated with substance abuse. Most respondents believe that females engaged in substance abuse do not usually exhibit antisocial behaviors. Overall, the majority agree that reducing or avoiding substance abuse would positively impact social interactions and adjustment for female students. The aggregate mean score suggests that respondents perceive substance abuse as having a predominantly negative influence on the social adjustment of Social Studies female students in the selected Colleges of Education.

Research Question Two: Perception of female students on the influence of substance abuse on emotional adjustment among Social Studies students in the selected Colleges of Education.

Table 2: Perceived substance abuse influence on emotional adjustment among Social Studies female students in the selected Colleges of Education by respondents (n=304)

S/N	Influence of substance abuse on emotional adjustment	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev.
1	Females with a substance abuse habit perceive a lack of genuine affection and love in their surroundings.	109(35.9)	158(52.0)	22(7.2)	15(4.9)	3.19	0.771
2	Substance abuse contributes to mood swings and emotional volatility among users.	159(52.3)	112(36.8)	25(8.2)	8(2.6)	3.39	0.749
3	Engaging in substance abuse leads to heightened emotional distress and instability.	116(38.2)	121(39.8)	50(16.4)	17(5.6)	3.11	0.872
4	Even a minor setback can greatly upset females with substance abuse problems.	101(33.2)	125(41.1)	64(21.1)	14(4.6)	3.03	0.854
5	Substance abuse can lead individuals to believe that they are failures.	122(40.1)	135(44.4)	36(11.8)	11(3.6)	3.21	0.789
6	Females with substance abuse problems struggle with receiving criticism.	132(43.4)	122(40.1)	42(13.8)	8(2.6)	3.24	0.788
7	Females with substance abuse problems often experience feelings of inferiority.	96(31.6)	141(46.4)	55(18.1)	12(3.9)	3.06	0.808
8	Females with substance abuse problem experience increased anxiety and depression.	165(54.3)	95(31.3)	30(9.9)	14(4.6)	3.35	0.839
9	Females with substance abuse habits have difficulty expressing love towards their friends and family.	107(35.2)	128(42.1)	50(16.4)	19(6.3)	3.06	0.875
10	Substance abuse negatively influences their self-esteem and self-confidence.	99(32.6)	121(39.8)	66(21.7)	18(5.9)	2.99	0.884
Aggregate mean						3.16	0.465

(Benchmark = 2.50)

The study in Table 2 focuses on the impact of substance abuse on the emotional adjustment of Social Studies female students in selected Colleges of Education. The findings highlight overwhelmingly negative influences, with a majority of respondents agreeing that substance abuse leads to a perceived lack of genuine affection and love in the users' surroundings. Additionally, substance abuse is

associated with mood swings, emotional distress, and instability. The study reveals that even minor setbacks can greatly upset individuals with substance abuse problems, and such habits may lead to a belief in personal failure.

Further negative emotional effects include struggles with receiving criticism, feelings of inferiority, increased anxiety and depression, and difficulty expressing love towards friends and family. The study emphasizes that substance abuse negatively influences self-esteem and self-confidence. The aggregate mean score of 3.16 suggests a significant overall negative impact of substance abuse on the emotional adjustment of Social Studies female students in the selected Colleges of Education in the North West zone of Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

This study assessed perception of substance abuse's implications on socio-emotional and psychological aspects among female Social Studies students in Colleges of Education of North-West, Nigeria. Social adjustment and emotional adjustments were the variables used for this study. The study found that substance abuse was perceived to have some positive influence on social adjustment among the female students. These influences included enhanced willingness of female students to address social problems, increases in the likelihood of forming friendships among female students among others. The findings revealed that overall, the negative aspects of substance abuse dominated in the social adjustment. Among the negative influence, study revealed, were that most female students indulging in substance abuse usually display antisocial behaviours, always associated with conflicts, disagreements in their interpersonal relationships, contributes to neglect of cultural values within the society and exclusion from social activities due to antisocial behaviours among others.

Influence of substance abuse was found to be negative on the emotional adjustment of Social Studies female students in the selected Colleges of Education. The study revealed that females with substance abuse habit perceive a lack of genuine affection and love in their surroundings and have mood swings and emotional volatility along with heightened emotional distress and instability. It was revealed that even minor setback can greatly upset such individuals and can lead them to believe that they are failures. It was revealed that such individuals struggle with receiving criticism and often experience feelings of inferiority. Among other emotional adjustment problems revealed from the findings were increased anxiety and depression, difficulty expressing love towards their friends and family members', negative self-esteem and self-confidence among others. The finding is consistent with Shaffer (2019) who reported that emotional adjustment is a way for a person to deal with the demands and stresses of their surroundings while still maintaining the internal and outward balance of their personality.

Conclusion

From the findings of the assessment carried out in this study, the research wishes to conclude that substance abuse has major negative influence on social adjustment of female students involved in the selected Colleges of Education of North West, Nigeria.

The emotional adjustment of female students involved in substance abuse is negatively influenced by such act in the selected Colleges of Education of North West, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following were recommended for this study:

- i. Develop and implement targeted substance abuse prevention programs within Colleges of Education to raise awareness about the negative consequences of substance abuse.

- ii. Strengthen emotional support services within educational institutions to assist female students in coping with emotional challenges associated with substance abuse. This can include counseling services and mental health resources.
- iii. Conduct educational campaigns focused on attitude change, challenging and changing perceptions related to substance abuse. This could include awareness programs that highlight the importance of maintaining a positive attitude toward academics and personal development.
- iv. Establish partnerships with local organizations and support groups that specialize in substance abuse prevention and rehabilitation. This collaboration can provide additional resources and expertise to address the issue.

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